

STARTING EMPIRICAL ANTIBACTERIAL THERAPY FOR BACTERIAL DESTRUCTIVE PNEUMONIA IN CHILDREN

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Summary

Many scientific works have been devoted to the treatment of acute bacterial destruction of the lungs in children, and scientists of different generations have formed the basic principles for the diagnosis and treatment of this pathology at the present stage. Despite this, the incidence of destructive pneumonia in children does not tend to decrease and remains one of the causes of child mortality. All this necessitates a more thorough study of the etiopathogenesis and clinic of this pathology.

Keywords. Acute bacterial destructive pneumonia, thoracentesis, children, empiric antibiotic therapy.

Relevance. Acute bacterial destructive pneumonia (ABDP) in children has been and remains one of the most severe diseases of childhood, causing serious damage to the health of the child [2,11,19]. ABDP are severe pathological conditions characterized by inflammatory infiltration and subsequent purulent or putrefactive decay (destruction) of the lung tissue [1,3,12,18]. All this largely determines the level of medical care for patients with bacterial destruction of the lungs in children. Despite the success achieved in the diagnosis and treatment of acute bacterial destructive pneumonia in children, it remains a formidable pathology in children and is one of the main causes of child mortality, which forces scientists to continue studying the features of this pathology. Thanks to the development of antibiotic therapy, many severe forms of community-acquired pneumonia in the absence of indications for surgical intervention are no longer treated in surgical, but in pediatric departments. However, mortality from destructive pneumonia, according to the literature, ranges from 3 to 15% [].

Depending on the state of the patient's body's defenses, the pathogenicity of the microflora, the ratio of damaging and regenerative processes in the lungs, either the delimitation of necrotic areas occurs, or the progressive spread of purulent-putrefactive fusion of the lung tissue [4,7,13,16].

In the etiology of ABDP, the main role is played by gram positive and gram negative flora, in addition, in most cases a viral infection is identified, which, according to some authors, is a factor against which the respiratory tract is damaged with the development of severe damage to the lung tissue [5,8,14,15]. Behind the last decade there has been a gradual displacement of staphylococcus from etiological agents due to a wide range of gram-negative flora (1,5,14,23).

The complexity of treating children with severe forms of pneumonia is explained by many problems and difficulties that arise at different stages of patient routing, starting from the outpatient period: underestimation of the severity of the condition, late prescription of antibacterial and antiviral therapy, untimely X-ray examination. To date, the issue of early

detection of ABDP pathogens has not been resolved, which does not allow the initiation of targeted and immediate antibiotic therapy [2,14,18]. Treatment of patients with ADBP is carried out in a complex manner using surgical and medical methods aimed at reorganizing the focus, stopping the intoxication syndrome and activating the body's anti-infective resistance.[8,10,13,20]. To date, the issue of early detection of ODBP pathogens in the first hours of the patient's admission to the hospital has not been resolved, which does not allow for immediate and targeted effective antibiotic therapy.[4,6,7,15,19,22]. Despite all of the above ongoing treatment, morbidity and mortality from this pathology does not tend to decrease. All this indicates the presence of unresolved and controversial issues in relation to the diagnosis and treatment of ABDP in children, which indicate the need for further study of this pathology and improvement of the treatment method [6,12,17,23].

Aim of study: Analysis of the results of initial empiric therapy in acute bacterial destructive pneumonia in children.

Material and methods. We analyzed the results of the treatment of ABDP in 74 children aged from 1 month to 14 years, who were treated at the pediatric surgery clinic of the Bukhara State Medical Institute, for the period 2020-2022. When analyzing patients admitted to the hospital, the pulmonary form was found in 25 (34%) cases, the pulmonary-pleural form was found in 49 (66%) patients. Of these, 42 (57%) patients underwent surgical intervention in the form of thoracentesis and the imposition of passive drainage according to the Bulau method, thoracotomy was performed in 3 (4%) patients, the remaining 29 (39%) patients were treated with a puncture method. When studying the etiological structure of ABDP obtained with a tank sowing, we used two indicators: the frequency of detection of the pathogen from among all examined and from among the positive results of the tank of sowing. Analysis of the results of bacteriological studies of purulent contents in 39 patients showed that more than half of the cases - 21 (54%) the causative agent of the purulent process was St.aureus, in other cases the following results were obtained: E. coli - 6 (15%), Ps.aeroginoza - 4 (10%), St.epidermidis - 2 (5%), Marked association microorganisms, more often staphylococcus with Pseudomonas aeruginosa and Escherichia coli - (8%) and the result of "no growth" was registered in 3 (8%) cases.

Considering that antibiotic therapy is urgent, it would be rational to prescribe antibiotics targeted, taking into account the pathogen and its sensitivity to antibiotics. Due to the low frequency of registration of pathogens and the duration of the study, traditional methods of bacteriological study of the focus of destruction do not allow the initiation of targeted, timely antibiotic therapy. In addition, it is often impossible to obtain material for a tank sowing from the focus of the pathological process (inflammatory infiltrate, pneumothorax, bullae, fibrinous pleurisy). However, the determination of the causative agent of the disease at the initial stages of the disease is not realistic, therefore, at the initial stages, we prescribed antibiotics based on the staphylococcal etiology of the disease, or gram-negative, less often mixed. Antistaphylococcal antibiotics and broad-spectrum antibiotics, 3rd or 4th generation cephalosporins (ceftriaxone, rocephin, etc.) in combination with amnoglycosides, were used to treat OBDL, which clinically in most cases gave a positive result from the first days of treatment. As the results of bacteriological studies were obtained, antibiotics were prescribed taking into account the sensitivity of the isolated pathogens of the pathological process. Reducing intoxication, normalizing temperature, appetite, reducing the amount of content from the drainage tube and during puncture, improving breathing,

Conclusions. 1. The etiology of ABDP is most often bacterial in nature and is caused by a wide range of pathogens, among which staphylococcus aureus is the leader.

2. The outcome of ABDP largely depends on early diagnosis and initial, empirical antibiotic therapy and the subsequent prescription of antibiotics, taking into account the sensitivity of the isolated pathogens of the pathological process.

3. There is a need to the search for alternative approaches to determining the etiology of the ABDP pathogen that are not related to obtaining material from the lesion and traditional cultivation of bacteria.

References:

- 1.A.T. Akhmedov, & L.A. Narziev. (2023). PREDICTORS OF CARDIOVASCULAR COMPLICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC ISCHEMIC HEART DISEASE AFTER BYPASS SURGERY. *International Journal of Medical Sciences And Clinical Research*, 3(03), 68–77. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijmscr/Volume03Issue03-10>
- 2.A.T. Akhmedov, & Zh.R. Sharipov. (2023). THE ROLE OF CYTOKINES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION. *International Journal of Medical Sciences And Clinical Research*, 3(03), 59–67. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijmscr/Volume03Issue03-09>
- 3.Ahmedov, A., & Kamolov, F. (2023). ECHOCARDOGRAPHIC CHANGES IN PATIENTS WITH A SURVEY OF PNEUMONIA ASSOCIATED WITH CORONAVIRUS INFECTION COVID-19. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(3), 110–115. Retrieved from <https://researchcitations.com/index.php/ibmscr/article/view/883>
- 4.Akhmedov A.T. (2022). COMPARATIVE EVALUATION OF IMMUNOLOGICAL PARAMETERS OF LABORATORY ANIMALS WITH THYMUS AUTOIMPLANTATION IN THE DYNAMICS OF OBSERVATION. *International Journal of Medical Sciences And Clinical Research*, 2(11), 12–18. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijmscr/Volume02Issue11-03>
- 5.An early thoracoscope approach in necrotizing pneumonia in children: a report of three cases / N. Kalfa, H. Allal, M. Lopez et al. // *J. Laparoendosc. Adv. Surg. Tech. A.*-2005.-Vol. 15, No. 1.-P. 18-22.
- 1.Barova, N. K., Tarakanov, V. A., Tshipris, A. A., Stepkin, M. A., Ubilava, I. A., Gorkova, I. S., ... & Kulish, T. A. (2013). Modern medical technologies in the treatment of acute destructive pneumonia in children. *Kuban Scientific Medical Bulletin*, (7), 58-59.
- 6.Bauer, TT Comparison of systemic cytokine levels in patients with acute respiratory distress syndrome, severe pneumonia, and controls / TT Bauer, C. Monton, A. Torres//*Thorax*. 2000. - Vol. 55, No. 1.-p. 1138-1145.
- 7.Beloborodova, N. V., Tarakanov, V. A., & Barova, N. K. (2016). Analysis of the causes of destructive pneumonia in children and the possibility of optimizing antimicrobial therapy. *Pediatrics. Journal them. GN Speransky*, 95(2), 66-71.
- 8.Clinical experience of managing empyema thoracic in children / FL Huang, PY Chen, JS Ma et al. // *J. Microbiol. Immunol. Infect.* 2002. - Vol. 35, No. 2. -P. 115-120.
- 9.Danilova, V. V., Bevz, S. I., Ovcharenko, S. S., Gurina, I. V., & Grigorova, M. V. (2018). To the question of the treatment of destructive pneumonia in children (Doctoral dissertation).
- 10.Diagnostic efficacy and prognostic value of serum procalcitonin concentration in patients with suspected sepsis / MJ Ruiz-Alvarez, S. Garc-a-Valdecasas, R. De Pablo et al. // *J. Intens. Care Med*. 2009. - Vol. 24, No. 1. - P. 63-71.

11. Dobrovolsky, S.R. Diagnosis and treatment of exudative pleurisy / S.R. Dobrovolsky, A.V. Belostotsky // Surgery. 2002. - No. 3. - S.52-57.
12. F.S., R. (2023). Morphological Features of the Ceca in the Area of Sphincters in White Laboratory Rats in Early Postnatal Ontogenesis. Scholastic: Journal of Natural and Medical Education, 2(4), 142-145.
13. F.S., R. (2023). Morphological Features of the Ceca in the Area of Sphincters in White Laboratory Rats in Early Postnatal Ontogenesis. Scholastic: Journal of Natural and Medical Education, 2(4), 142-145. Retrieved from <http://univerpubl.com/index.php/scholastic/article/view/1124>
14. Gisak S. N., Chernykh A. V., Vecherkin V. A. et al. / Modern changes in the pathomorphosis of pathogens of acute purulent destruction of the lungs and pleura in children. Proceedings of the Russian Symposium "Purulent-inflammatory diseases of the lungs and pleura in children" Krasnodar-Sochi. 2015 -p.5.
15. Isakov Yu.F., Stepanov E.A., Razumovsky A.Yu. /New technologies in pediatric surgery// Modern technologies in pediatrics and pediatric surgery: mater. IV Congr. M., 2005. - S. 334.
16. Kobilov, E. E., Raupov, F. S., & Mekhriddinov, M. K. (2020). A modern approach to the treatment of acute bacterial lung destruction in children. A new day in medicine, (4), 312-315.
17. Mashkov, A. E., Shcherbina, V. I., Tsuman, V. G., Druzyuk, E. Z., Surovikina, M. S., Nalivkt, A. E., ... & Slesarev, V. V. (2005). Modern aspects of the treatment of complicated forms of acute destructive pneumonia in children. Almanac of Clinical Medicine, (8-1), 240-249.
18. Mekhriddinov, M. K. (2022). Modern view on the problems of etiopathogenesis and treatment of destructive forms of pneumonia in children. Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 3(2), 248-255.
19. Mekhriddinov, M. K. (2022). The role of immunological factors in the pathogenesis of the development of destructive forms of pneumonia in children. Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 3(2), 234-238.
20. Pogorelov M. V., Danilovskikh D. A., Abushkin I. A. et al. / Analysis of antibiotic therapy in children with purulent-inflammatory diseases of the lungs and pleura at the stages of treatment. //Materials of the Russian Symposium "Purulent-inflammatory diseases of the lungs and pleura in children" Krasnodar-Sochi. 2015 -p.15.
21. Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaymonovich, D. S. (2022). Physical activity and its impact on human health and longevity. Достижения науки и образования, (2 (82)), 120-126.
22. Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaymonovich, D. S. (2022). THE CONCEPT OF "HEALTHY LIFESTYLE" IN PSYCHOLOGICAL RESEARCH. ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions, 3(06), 53-64.
23. Raupov, F. S., & Kobilov, E. E. EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF OZONE THERAPY FOR PURULENT SURGICAL INFECTION IN CHILDREN. LBC 57.33: 54.5 C 56, 77.
24. Raupov, F. S., & Mekhriddinov, M. K. (2021). Results of the Complex Treatment of Acute Bacterial Destruction of the Lungs in Children. Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 146-149. <https://doi.org/10.47494/cajms.vi0.366>
25. Raupov, F.S. (2020). Possible dysfunctions of the large intestine after resection in children. Problems of Biology and Medicine, (3), 119.
26. Sap N. A., Olenina N. V., Nekrasova E. G., Alexandrova N. S. / Thoracoscopy in acute purulent-destructive pneumonia in children. //Materials of the Russian Symposium "Purulent-inflammatory diseases of the lungs and pleura in children" Krasnodar-Sochi. 2015 -p.22.

- 27.Savenkova, M. S., Vrublevsky, S. G., Koltunov, I. E., Persianinova, E. S., Semenova, L. P., Anin, A. N., ... & Kurenkov, I. V. (2015). Destructive pneumonia in children: complex issues of diagnosis and choice of individual etiopathogenetic therapy. *Farmateka*, 14, 34-40.
- 28.Sh, Navruzova, and A.T. Akhmedov. "Autoimplantation Of Thymus In Surgical Correction Of Congenital Heart Defects." *Central Asian Journal Of Medical And Natural Sciences* 2.3 (2021): 88-98.
- 29.Shamsiev, A.M. Acute destructive pneumonia in children / AM Shamsiev. -Tashkent, 1996.- 215 p.
- 30.Vecherkin, V. A., Toma, D. A., Ptitsyn, V. A., & Koryashkin, P. V. (2019). Destructive pneumonia in children. *Russian Bulletin of Pediatric Surgery, Anesthesiology and Resuscitation*, 9(4), 108-115.
- 31.Yusupov, Sh., Pulatov, P., Bazarov, B., & Zhaniev, H. (2015). Diagnosis and treatment of acute destructive pneumonia in children. *Journal of Problems of Biology and Medicine*, (1 (82)), 124-127.
- 32.Ахмедов А.Т., Особенности иммунной системы при врожденных пороках сердца, // EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2022. Vol. 2 No. 3 EJMMMP. – С. 35-40. [Akhmedov A. T., Features of the immune system in congenital heart defects, // EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2022. Vol. 2 no. 3 EJMMMP. – pp. 35-40 [in Russian]
- 33.Ахмедов А.Т., Сравнительная оценка иммунологических параметров лабораторных животных аутоимплантации тимуса в динамике наблюдения, // EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2022. - Vol. 2 No. 3: EJMMMP. С. 40-45 [Akhmedov A. T., Comparative evaluation of the immunological parameters of laboratory animals after thymus autoimplantation in the dynamics of observation, // EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE. - 2022. - Vol. 2 no. 3: EJMMMP. С. 40-45 in Russian]
- 34.Хидояттов, Б. А. Микроциркуляторное русло кишечника и поджелудочной железы и его особенности при экспериментальном сахарном диабете / Б. А. Хидояттов, А. Т. Ахмедов // Морфология. – 2008. – Т. 133. – № 2. – С. 145-146. – EDN JUTXTT.7. Otto CM, Pearlman AS Textbook of clinical echocardiography. Philadelphia: WB Saunders Co.; 1995:418.
- 35.Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaimonovich, D. S. (2023). Influence of the Mode of Work and Recreation of the Student's Health. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HEALTH SYSTEMS AND MEDICAL SCIENCES*, 2(3), 3-5.
- 36.Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaymonovich, D. S. (2023). Forming a Healthy Lifestyle for Students on the Example of the Volleyball Section in Universities. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 3(3), 22-25.
- 37.Джалилова, З. О., Хасанов, К. А., & Султонов, А. А. (2021). Роль научного управления в процессе обучения высококвалифицированных врачей в новом Узбекистане. *Молодой ученый*, (26), 377-379.

